

Aluminium-Nicotine Exchange Equilibria on Illite (Part II)

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Manuscript received 29 March 1975; revised 17 July 1975; accepted 8 August 1975

Aluminium-nicotine exchange equilibria in dilute suspensions of illite were studied at 25° and 40°. Exchange isotherms were drawn and thermodynamic equilibrium constants and the standard free energies of exchange were evaluated from the selectivity coefficients. The results indicated a preference of nicotine by the clay system at both the temperatures upto a limited concentration. The negative enthalpy effects and entropy loss accompanying the reaction showed a stronger and more ordered binding of the nicotine ions on the clay surface. Values of surface phase activity coefficients of the adsorbed ions and the excess thermodynamic functions indicated that the equilibria involving aluminium and nicotine behaved as a non-ideal system.

ILLITE occurs widely as a constituent of illitic soils. Its ion exchange properties have been of considerable interest both for theoretical and practical reasons. The toxicity and acidity of aluminium in soils is of considerable interest. Clays show a strong preference for aluminium ion in dilute solutions and it is almost impossible to exchange it with other ions. Such, however, is not the case with concentrated solutions¹.

Nicotine is a base and a pesticide. It plays an important role in the functions of the central nervous system. Studies in these laboratories^{2,3} and elsewhere⁴ revealed that acidic illites interact stoichiometrically with nicotine and other heterocyclic bases. The interaction was a base exchange one, in which, the adsorption of nicotine occurred upto the base exchange capacity.

In the study of ion exchange it has been recognised that although the two ions may exchange stoichiometrically, they would not, in general, be held equally strongly by the exchanger. Preference by the exchanger plays an important role in ion exchange reactions. Thus, it became desirable to study in detail the ion exchange reactions into which aluminium and nicotine participate in terms of the thermodynamic functions and surface phase activity coefficients. The basis of the treatment have been the thermodynamic formulations of previous workers⁵⁻⁸. It has been felt that such a study will throw considerable light on the mechanism of nicotine adsorption and release on aluminium illites.

Experimental

The clay mineral illite used in these studies was from Morris, Illinois and was a monomineralic standard of the clay mineral standards Project No. 49 of the American Petroleum Institute. The less than two micron clay fraction was isolated by sedimentation

and centrifugation at a speed of 3000 rpm by filtering through the bowl of the "International Chemical" centrifuge. The clay suspension was equilibrated with 2*N* NaCl and 0.1*N* HCl for half an hour. The supernatant salt solution was decanted. This treatment was repeated three times and chloride ions removed from the sodium clay suspension by washing with distilled water till the clay dispersed and till the filtrate was free of chloride ions.

To obtain aluminium illite the sodium illite suspension was treated with normal aluminium chloride solution. The suspension was then washed with distilled water till the resistance of the suspension became of the same order as that of distilled water. The concentration of the suspension was 1.28 g/100 ml and its *pH* = 4.0.

Nicotine was purified by distilling at 98° and 4 mm pressure in an inert atmosphere.

For the determination of exchange isotherms, 10.0 ml each of aluminium illite suspension was taken in different stoppered glass tubes. Various concentrations of standard nicotine solution (0.5 g per 100 ml) were immediately added and the mixture adjusted to 25 ml with distilled water. The tubes were shaken at 25° ± 0.1° in the first set of experiments and 40° ± 0.1° in the second set of experiments for 24 hr in a thermostatic bath. The mixtures were then centrifuged immediately and aluminium and nicotine in the supernatant liquid estimated. The aluminium was estimated colorimetrically using aluminon⁹ as colour reagent and nicotine with standard hydrochloric acid using methyl red as indicator. The CEC of illite was measured by the ammonium acetate method of Jackson¹⁰. The corresponding concentrations of aluminium in the clay phase were obtained by difference (CEC minus concentration of cation in the supernatant liquid) and that for nicotine from nicotine added minus the nicotine in the supernatant liquid.

Results and Discussion

The interaction in the aluminium-nicotine system in dilute suspensions can be described by the equation

where bars represent the equivalent concentration of the ion concerned in the solid phase and unbarred quantities the electrolyte concentration in solution.

The equivalent ionic fractions of aluminium and nicotine in illite and in the solution were calculated from the expressions

$$\bar{X}_{Al} = \frac{C_{Al}}{\bar{C}}, \quad X_{Al} = \frac{C_{Al}}{C}, \quad \bar{X}_{nicotine} = \frac{\bar{C}_{nicotine}}{\bar{C}}$$

and $X_{nicotine} = \frac{C_{nicotine}}{C}$, where \bar{C} was the total electrolyte concentration in the clay phase and C that in the solution ($\bar{C} = C_{Al} + \bar{C}_{nicotine}$ and $C = C_{Al} + C_{nicotine}$). The values obtained both at 25° and 40° are given in Table 1. A plot of these values gave exchange isotherms as in Fig. 1. At both the tem-

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherms of nicotine on aluminium illite at 25° and 40°.

peratures the isotherms were sigmoid and showed selectivity reversal. Nicotine was strongly preferred by the clay upto an equivalent ionic fraction of 0.64 of nicotine at 25° and upto 0.62 of nicotine at 40°. Thereafter the aluminium preference for illite showed an upward trend.

To examine the interaction in the clay phase, the selectivity coefficients at 25° and 40° for different surface compositions of nicotine were determined from the expression¹¹, (assuming the ratio of activity coefficients as unity¹² in the dilute range studied) :

$$K_C = \frac{(\bar{X}_{nicotine})^3 (X_{Al})}{(\bar{X}_{Al})(X_{nicotine})^3} \quad \dots (2)$$

The values are summarised in Table 1 and the effect of nicotine concentration on these values represented

TABLE I—VALUES OF EQUIVALENT IONIC FRACTIONS OF ALUMINIUM AND NICOTINE AND SELECTIVITY QUOTIENTS AT 25° AND 40° FOR THE NICOTINE EXCHANGE ON ALUMINIUM ILLITE

(Set 25°)					
\bar{X}_{Al}	X_{Al}	$\bar{X}_{Nicotine}$	$X_{Nicotine}$	K_C	$\log K_C$
0.789	0.887	0.211	0.113	10.117	1.0051
0.648	0.844	0.352	0.156	14.327	1.1562
0.479	0.730	0.521	0.270	10.744	1.0310
0.337	0.168	0.663	0.831	0.252	-0.5986
0.208	0.097	0.792	0.902	0.315	-0.5017
0.196	0.045	0.804	0.955	0.135	-0.8697
0.184	0.038	0.815	0.962	0.125	-0.9031
0.174	0.033	0.826	0.966	0.118	-0.9281
0.152	0.031	0.847	0.969	0.136	-0.8665
0.136	0.029	0.864	0.971	0.150	-0.8239
(Set 40°)					
0.790	0.859	0.209	0.141	3.262	0.5135
0.646	0.818	0.353	0.181	9.285	0.9677
0.480	0.634	0.520	0.316	6.007	0.7787
0.343	0.139	0.657	0.860	0.180	-0.7447
0.240	0.064	0.760	0.936	0.142	-0.8477
0.227	0.044	0.773	0.956	0.102	-0.9914
0.188	0.052	0.812	0.948	0.173	-0.7620
0.139	0.063	0.860	0.937	0.350	-0.4559
0.113	0.053	0.887	0.946	0.386	-0.4134
0.100	0.044	0.900	0.956	0.367	-0.4353

as in Fig. 2. At both the temperatures the selectivity quotient after an initial rise decreased and then rose

Fig. 2. Logarithms of selectivity quotients vs equivalent ionic fraction of nicotine in illite at 25° and 40°.

again. Such a behaviour, in general, was indicative of the fact that at both the temperatures beyond

a certain concentration, the preference of the solid surface for nicotine decreased with a rise in its concentration and thereafter rose again. It thus appeared that there were significant interactions between the nicotine and the multiple sites of aluminium illite which underwent gradual saturation one after another.

For a further study of the affinity the thermodynamic equilibrium constant K was calculated by the equation proposed by Gaines and Thomas⁶,

$$\ln K = (Z_A - Z_B) + \int_0^1 \ln K_c d\bar{X}_{nicotine} \quad \dots (3)$$

where Z_A and Z_B were the charges of the competing ions. Evaluating the integral with the help of trapezoidal rule and substituting the other values, the values of K at 25° and 40° were calculated. The value of K at 25° was higher than that at 40° indicating that nicotine had a higher affinity for the aluminium clay at 25° than at 40°. The interaction was temperature dependent.

The standard free energy of exchange ΔG° for the interaction was calculated using the relation

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad \dots (4)$$

The standard enthalpy change ΔH° was calculated from the Vant' Hoff isochore

$$\ln \left(\frac{KT_2}{KT_1} \right) = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right) \quad \dots (5)$$

and the standard entropy change by the equation

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad \dots (6)$$

The values obtained are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC VALUES FOR THE NICOTINE EXCHANGE WITH ALUMINIUM ILLITE AT 25° AND 40°

Thermodynamic parameters	25°	40°
K	25.79	14.88
ΔG° Cal/mole	-1927.02	-1668.79
ΔH° Cal/mole	-7057.09	
ΔS° Cal/mole	-17.21	

The negative values of ΔG° both at 25° and 40° indicated that the illite surface had a higher preference for nicotine than aluminium; that at 25° being still higher than at 40°.

The negative enthalpy effects showed that the adsorption of nicotine decreased with rise in temperature. The decrease in enthalpy indicated that nicotine was more strongly bound to the clay surface than aluminium and the exchange of nicotine with aluminium may not be easy in the concentration range studied.

The adsorption of nicotine was accompanied by entropy loss. The decrease in entropy indicated a reversible system with nicotinium ions forming a very well placed ordered arrangement in the Stern

layer and aluminium ions forming a diffused arrangement in the Gouy layer¹³. This fact was in accordance with the preference shown by the illite surface for nicotine.

The surface activity coefficients of aluminium and nicotinium ions at the surface were calculated from the following expressions¹⁴:

$$\ln f_{Al} = \bar{X}_{nicotine} \ln K_C - \int_0^{\bar{X}_{nicotine}} \ln K_C d\bar{X}_{nicotine} \quad \dots (7)$$

and

$$\ln f_{nicotine} = (\bar{X}_{nicotine} - 1) \ln K_C - \int_0^{\bar{X}_{nicotine}} \ln K_C d\bar{X}_{nicotine} \quad \dots (8)$$

The values are given in Table 3 and were plotted against mole fraction ($\bar{X}_{nicotine}$) (Figs. 3-4). The

Fig. 3. The surface activity coefficient for different aluminium-nicotine compositions at the clay surface at 25° and 40°.

Fig. 4. The surface phase activity coefficient for different aluminium-nicotine compositions at the clay surface at 25° and 40°.

absence of similarity in the plots of the surface phase activity coefficients f_{Al} and $f_{nicotine}$ against ionic fraction of nicotine indicated that both nicotine and aluminium behaved differently on the illite surface (Table 3). At both the temperatures, upto an equivalent ionic fraction of 0.52 of nicotine the values of surface phase activity coefficient of aluminium were greater than unity while those of nicotine were throughout less than unity. Significantly beyond this equivalent ionic fraction these values became less than unity in case of aluminium also. The deviation of the activity coefficients from unity indicated a heterogeneous distribution of the ions at the clay surface. Thus, it seemed that the distribution and the freedom of movement of the two ions in the Gouy and Stern layers varied according to the concentration of nicotine added to Al-illite. The results found support from the work of Deist and Talibudeen¹⁵ on ion exchange in soils.

TABLE 3—ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT OF THE ADSORBED IONS AS A FUNCTION OF NICOTINE FRACTION IN ILLITE AT 25° AND 40°

Values at 25°			Values at 40°		
$\bar{X}_{Nicotine}$	f_{Al}	$f_{Nicotine}$	$\bar{X}_{Nicotine}$	f_{Al}	$f_{Nicotine}$
0.211	1.271	0.126	0.209	1.127	0.346
0.352	1.391	0.097	0.353	1.522	0.164
0.521	1.221	0.113	0.520	1.234	0.204
0.663	0.107	0.427	0.657	0.135	0.726
0.792	0.098	0.313	0.760	0.093	0.657
0.804	0.050	0.368	0.773	0.071	0.705
0.815	0.045	0.372	0.812	0.110	0.638
0.826	0.045	0.383	0.860	0.198	0.565
0.847	0.050	0.375	0.887	0.216	0.560
0.864	0.055	0.372	0.900	0.206	0.560

TABLE 4—EXCESS FREE ENERGIES, ENTHALPIES AND ENTROPIES OF MIXING, ΔG_m^x , ΔH_m^x AND ΔS_m^x FOR ALUMINIUM-NICOTINE EXCHANGE ON ILLITE AT 25° AND 40°

(Set 25°)			
$\bar{X}_{Nicotine}$	ΔG_m^x	ΔH_m^x	ΔS_m^x
0.211	-146.77	-1378.41	-4.13
0.352	-358.42	-2845.19	-8.34
0.521	-616.62	-3675.77	-10.26
0.663	-780.24	-5177.89	-14.76
0.792	-832.90	-6750.69	-19.85
0.804	-825.25	-6962.76	-20.59
0.815	-811.07	-6945.08	-20.58
0.826	-788.12	-6768.36	-20.07
0.847	-761.61	-6573.97	-19.50
0.864	-740.74	-6291.22	-18.59
(Set 40°)			
$\bar{X}_{Nicotine}$	ΔG_m^x	ΔH_m^x	ΔS_m^x
0.209	-79.17	-1501.18	-4.54
0.353	-227.53	-3138.83	-9.16
0.520	-452.39	-4035.64	-11.45
0.657	-563.88	-5692.78	-16.39
0.760	-556.53	-7135.47	-21.02
0.773	-543.27	-7544.89	-22.37
0.812	-488.95	-7681.36	-22.99
0.860	-446.78	-6960.01	-20.81
0.887	-428.85	-6745.56	-20.18
0.900	-423.05	-6511.61	-19.13

The values of surface activity coefficients (Table 3) indicated that the system under investigation did not behave ideally. The excess thermodynamic functions for such a non-ideal system were calculated by the equations^{16,17} :

$$\Delta G_m^x = RT[\bar{X}_{nicotine} \ln f_{nicotine} + \bar{X}_{Al} \ln f_{Al}] \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\Delta H_m^x = -RT^2 \left[\bar{X}_{nicotine} \left(\frac{\partial \ln f_{nicotine}}{\partial T} \right) + \bar{X}_{Al} \left(\frac{\partial \ln f_{Al}}{\partial T} \right) \right] \quad \dots (10)$$

and

$$\Delta G_m^x = \Delta H_m^x - T\Delta S_m^x \quad \dots (11)$$

where ΔG_m^x , ΔH_m^x and ΔS_m^x were the excess free energy, enthalpy and entropy of mixing. The values are given in Table 4. A plot of the excess free energy of mixing against $\bar{X}_{nicotine}$ is given in Fig. 5. At both the temperatures the excess free

Fig. 5. The excess free energy change of mixing against the equivalent fraction of nicotine on the clay at 25° and 40°.

energies of mixing were negative, the value first increased and thereafter decreased with increasing concentration of $\bar{X}_{nicotine}$. It thus appeared that the heterogeneous mixture of aluminium and nicotine ions on the illite surface was initially more stable as compared to the pure homoionic forms and thereafter became less or more stable depending upon the concentration of nicotine. Thus, deviation from ideality occurred in the form of a more or less stable mixture depending upon the equivalent ionic fraction of nicotine.

Negative enthalpies and entropies of mixing (Table 4) indicated that the ions were strongly bound with each other at the clay surface and the

distribution of the mixture of aluminium and nicotine ions was more ordered than the heteroionic exchange with respect to the pure homoionic forms.

Acknowledgement

The second author is indebted to C.S.I.R. for the grant of a senior fellowship.

References

1. P. NYE, D. CRAIG, N. T. COLEMAN and J. L. ROGLAND, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.* 1961, **25**, 14.
2. S. U. KHAN and J. P. SINGHAL, *Soil Sci.*, 1967, **104**, 427.
3. J. P. SINGHAL and R. P. SINGH, *Electroanal. Chem. and Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1973, **43**, 145.
4. C. R. SMITH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1561.
5. W. J. ARGERSINGER, W. A. DAVIDSON and O. D. BONNER, *Kansas Acad. Sci. Trans.*, 1950, **53**, 404.
6. G. L. GAINES, Jr. and H. C. THOMAS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, **21**, 714.
7. J. P. SINGHAL and R. P. SINGH, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1973, **24**, 271.
8. F. HELFFERICH, "Ion Exchange". Series in Advanced Chemistry. McGraw-Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, 1962.
9. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals". Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1959.
10. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis". Prentice and Hall, Inc., N.J., 1959.
11. D. REICHENBERG, "Ion Exchange Selectivity". In J. A. Marinsky (ed.) Ion exchange a series in advances. Vol. I, Chap. 7, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1966.
12. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths, London, 1959.
13. J. P. SINGHAL, R. P. SINGH and D. KUMAR, *Coll. Polym. Sci.*, 1975, **139**, 253.
14. D. G. HOWERY and H. C. THOMAS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 531.
15. I. DEIST and O. TALIBUDEEN, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1967, **18**, 138.
16. E. F. VANSANT and J. B. UYTTERHOEVEN, *Clays and Clay Minerals*, 1972, **20**, 47.
17. R. G. GAST and W. D. KLOBE, *Clays and Clay Minerals*, 1971, **19**, 311.